

Sociodemographic Predictors of Knowledge and Practice of Stroke Preventive Strategies among Healthcare Workers in a Tertiary Hospital in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Introduction: Stroke occurrence and morbidity are on the increase in Sub-Saharan Africa. Knowledge and practice of stroke prevention with prompt response to symptoms or warning signs are essential elements of a timely diagnosis and disease management. We evaluated Sociodemographic predictors of knowledge and practice of stroke prevention among healthcare workers in Nigeria.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study designed among 200 Healthcare workers in the Federal Medical Center, Asaba, Nigeria. They were selected by systematic sampling technique. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data on the research variables. Data were analyzed using the IBM SPSS version 25 statistical package.

Results: One hundred and thirteen were female clinical Health workers (54.5%), who were married (63%) and above 30 years (72%)

of age. They had good aggregate knowledge (84%) of stroke prevention but with poor practice (61%). There was a significant association between good knowledge of stroke with gender, age above 30 years, having tertiary education, and profession. However, their poor practice of stroke prevention was significant with gender and profession. We found age (95%CI= 0.082-0.865, p=0.028) and profession (95%CI= 0.033-0.350, p=0.0001) as the predictors of good knowledge of stroke prevention, while gender (95%CI=1.771-7.030, p=0.0001) and profession (95%CI=0.167-0.693, p=0.003) as the predictors of poor practice of stroke prevention among Healthcare workers.

Conclusions: These findings suggest the need for older, tertiary-educated clinical Health workers to engage actively in both patients' education and public and government enlightenment campaigns to halt the rising burden of stroke across the globe.

Keywords: *Socio-demographic, Predictor, Knowledge, Practice, Stroke, Prevention.*

Introduction

Stroke was the third-leading cause of Mortality and disability jointly and the second-leading cause of death worldwide in 2017, afflicting about 13 million people annually (GBD 2017 DALYs and HALE Collaborators, 2018; Krishnamurthi, Ikeda, & Feigin, 2020; Lindsay, et al., 2019).

In Africa, data available within the past 10 years showed that stroke has a yearly incidence rate of up to 316 per 100,000, a prevalence of up to 1,460 per 100,000, and a 3-year mortality rate greater than 80% (Akinyemi, et al., 2021). In Nigeria between the last two decades, 30-day case fatality rates ranging from 21.2% to 40% was reported (Erameh, Emorinken, & Akpasubi, 2023; Ekeh, et al., 2015; Mohammedm et al., 2021). The Global Stroke Factsheet8 brought out in 2022 indicated that the likelihood of having a stroke in one's lifetime has increased by 50% over the last decade and 1 in 4 people is predicted to have a stroke in their lifetime. From 1990 to 2019, there has been a 70% surge in stroke manifestation, a 43% increase in deaths due to stroke, a 102% rise in stroke incidence, and a 143% rise in Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) (Feigin, et a., 2022). The most notable feature is that the majority of the worldwide stroke problem (86% of deaths from stroke and 89% of DALYs) happens in poorer and lesser-middle-income nations (Feigin, et a., 2022). This problem faced by these low and middle-income countries has placed an unequaled problem on

families with less income. WHO-backed policies help to control the weight of stroke through primordial, primary, and secondary prevention and rehabilitation (Feigin, et a., 2022). The major signs (CDC, FAST, 2022) of this brain disease are facial drooping, arm weakness on one side, and speaking difficulties slurring or not logical, changes in sight, and unsteadiness/dizziness (CDC, FAST, 2022).

Knowledge and practice of the emergency signs of stroke can save lives and increase the outcome for survivors; - "FAST" (facial drooping, arm weakness on one side, speech difficulty, timely intervention) (Crause, & Stassen, 2020). Stroke recognition assists any person in recognizing a stroke quickly and taking immediate action to transfer the patient to the nearest hospital (Václavík, et al., 2018). Stroke is largely preventable (Kalkonde, et al., 2018). Though efforts should be made to advance acute stroke care services in low-income countries, data from the developed countries proposes that strong importance on prevention would be desirable to reduce the burden of stroke. These measures would provide additional cross-cutting benefits (Kalkonde, et al., 2018). Therefore, insufficient knowledge of risk factors, warning signs, and urgent beneficial approaches have been acknowledged as a major cause of increased death and morbidity due to stroke (Chhabra, et al., 2019).

Likewise, in effect, the management of stroke depends mainly on the public's knowledge of its warning signs, which could aid in earlier

detection and better response rates (Kalehoff, & Oparil, 2020; Sayyad, et al., 2021). Consequently, it is important to measure individual patients' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (Alhowaymel, et al., 2023) (KAP) towards stroke prevention among the general population and explore the factors that may contribute to the KAP levels. Generally, people residing in the communities have less access to healthcare services. They have lower socioeconomic, and sociodemographic status compared to their counterparts in other areas which may influence their KAP toward stroke prevention (Alhowaymel, et al., 2023). There is a dearth of patients' knowledge and participation in the care of stroke especially in sub-Saharan Africa (Arisege, et al., 2018). This participation requires motivation, knowledge, and compliance from the patients since it is a complex lifetime routine that needs to be followed. Patients who do not have good knowledge of the risk factors, and warning signs of stroke are less likely to engage in stroke prevention practices like controlling their blood pressure and rejecting other behavioral, spiritual, and traditional practices. This may indirectly influence their knowledge and practice of stroke prevention (Arisege, et al., 2018). Considering the paucity of data on sociodemographic predictors of knowledge and practice of stroke prevention in Healthcare. This study was conducted to assess these factors and the findings would be valuable to policymakers, and other stakeholders in planning appropriate interventions for addressing the rising burden of stroke globally.

Methodology

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at Federal Medical Centre, Asaba (Odenigbo, & Oguejiofor, 2009). The study participants were Health Care Workers; doctors, nurses, pharmacists, physiotherapists, radiographers, laboratory scientists, health attendants, Administrative staff, workers, and other Hospital workers. They were grouped into two for the study. Those who worked directly with the patients in the wards. They had responsibilities related to diagnosis and

treatment. They were considered "Clinical Health Care workers" (Andrew, & Marley, 2020). This represented the Doctors and the Nurses. Those who did not work directly with the patients in the ward and had no responsibilities relating to diagnosis and treatment were considered "Non-clinical Health Care Workers" (Andrew, & Marley, 2020). This represented others.

The Health Care workers were sampled by using simple random sampling of systematic technique (Hayes, 2021). Purposive sampling of the non-probability method was used in sharing the sample size. Doctors 290, Nurses 480, Pharmacists 52, physiotherapists 20, Radiographers 20, Lab science 44, Health attendants 50, and other non-clinical health workers 485, giving a total of 1441 Health care workers. The Inclusion criteria were:

- 1) Those who have been in the employment of Federal Medical Centre for not less than 6 (6) months.
- 2) Those who were not in any way incapacitated.
- 3) Those who were willing to dispense information.
- 4) Those who gave consent and their confidentiality maintained. Those who did not give consent were excluded from the study.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample was derived using Taro Yamane's formula (Olonite, 2022) for sample size determination.

$$\frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} \quad (1)$$

Where e = level of precision = 0.05

N = population size = 335

n = sample size

$$\frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} = \frac{335}{1+335(0.0025)} = \frac{335}{1+0.8375} = \frac{335}{1.8375} = 182.31 \sim 182+10\%=200.$$

Total= 200 which was the sample size

Systematic random sampling (Donkor, et al., 2014) was used for each of the workgroups. The sampling interval was derived using the formula below: Sample interval = a Total number of health workers/Sample size. From the total list of healthcare workers in the different categories, a sampling ratio was calculated for each category giving an Nth number of 3,

n=200 sample size

N=1441 Total number of healthcare workers

Sampling fraction

200/1441

N= 0.1388

Doctors 290x 0.1388 = 40.25 approximate 40

Nurses=480x 0.1388=66.62 Ω 67

Pharmacist 52x 0.1388=7.21 Ω 7

Physiotherapist 20x 0.1388=2.78 Ω 3

Radiographers 20x 0.1388=2.78 Ω 3

Lab science 44x 0.1388= 6.11Ω 6

Health attendant=50x 0.1388=6.94 Ω 7

Contract staffs = 485x 0.1388= 67.32 Ω 67

1. Doctors – 290/40=7
2. Nurses-480/67=7
3. Pharmacist-52/7=7
4. Physiotherapist-20/3=7
5. Radiographers 20/3=7
6. Lab scientist 44/6=7
7. Health attendant 50/7=7
8. Other non-clinical staffs 485/67=7

Therefore every 7th Staff of the hospital in each category was recruited for the study until the total number was obtained.

Data Collection

The study was conducted by using a semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed with the help of reviewed literature in the empirical review of the study. It will consist of two parts: (1) Socio-demographic characteristics (age, gender, job designation, etc.). (2) Socio-demographic relationships with knowledge and practice of Health Care Workers on Primary Preventive Strategies of stroke.

The nature and purpose of the study were explained to each respondent and informed and written consent was obtained. The duration of the study was one month.

For the convenience of analyses, the total number of questions to assess knowledge and Practice were ten (10) and (11) respectively, each correct response was scored one (1) and for each wrong response zero (0). The total scores for each respondent were converted to percentage scores a score of > 50% was termed Good Knowledge or Practice and a score of < 50% was categorized as poor knowledge or Practice.

Method of Data Analysis

Data was screened for completeness, entered, and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS V. 25.0). Univariate analysis was carried out as quantitative variables. This was presented using percentages and frequencies. Aggregate scores were calculated on knowledge, and practice to know if knowledge and practice is high or low. Bivariate analysis was carried out between the socio-demographic variables of knowledge and practice, using chi-square and p-value to determine the level of significance. Logistic regression analysis was used to determine the variables that predict good knowledge and practice of stroke prevention. All levels of significance were set at p < 0.05.

Duration of the Study

This study was carried out within a month.

Ethical Issues / Consideration

Ethical permission to conduct this research was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee and the due processes in carrying out research in the hospital were maintained and no harm or discomfort to participants during the questionnaire distribution.

Privacy

The privacy of the respondents was of utmost importance during the conduct of the research. The rights of the individuals that were used as subjects of the research were protected. Respondents were not forced into participating in the research project.

Maintenance of Confidentiality

The research subject names were withheld, and information given was not divulged to other

people but rather was treated with utmost secrecy and strictly for the study.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of Respondents

Out of 200 study respondents, 113 (56.5%) of them were female and the majority 144 (72%) of them were 30 years and above with a mean age of 36.20 and SD \pm 10.60 years. Regarding religion; 96.5% of the respondents were Christians. The majority (97.5%) of them had tertiary education and 63% of them were married. More than half (54.5%) of the respondents were Clinical Healthcare workers (Table1).

Table1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency (N=200)	Percentage (100%)
Gender		
Male	87	43.5
Female	113	56.5
Age1(years)		
<= 30	56	28.0
>30	144	72.0
Age (in Years)		
<20	5	2.5
21-30	55	27.5
31-40	68	34.0
41-50	47	23.5
51-60	25	12.5
Marital Status		
Single	68	34.0
Married	126	63.0
Divorced	2	1.0
Widowed	4	3.0
Profession1		
Clinical Healthcare workers	109	54.5
Non-clinical Healthcare workers	91	45.5
Profession		
Medical doctor	40	20.0
Nurse	67	33.5
Pharmacist	7	3.5
Lab scientist	6	3.0
Radiographers	3	1.5
Physiotherapist	3	1.5
Health attendants	7	3.5
Other Non-clinical Health care workers	67	33.5
Education Level1		
Poorly Educated	7	3.5

Tertiary Educated	195	97.5
Educational Level		
No formal education	0	0.0
Primary education	3	1.5
Secondary education	4	2.0
Tertiary education	193	96.5
Religion		
Christianity	193	96.5
Muslim	3	1.5
Traditional	4	2

Knowledge of Stroke and its Prevention among Respondents

About 84% of the 200 Healthcare workers had good aggregate knowledge of stroke prevention. The stroke prevention knowledge most

commonly recognized by the respondents includes a declaration that stroke is preventable (93.5%) and if treated early (94.5%), will have an effect on individuals' daily life activities (95.5%). That stroke can become more devastating if occurs more than once (83%) (Table 2).

Table2. Knowledge of Stroke and its Prevention among Respondents

Knowledge Questions	Yes (%)	No (%)
The Organ of the body affected by stroke is the Brain	87.5	12.5
Is Stroke a Preventable disease	93.5	6.5
Can one have a stroke more than once	83.0	17.0
Does stroke affect daily activities like driving a car, dressing, having a job, etc	95.5	4.5
Can stroke be prevented if treated early	94.5	5.5
Do you know any risk factors for stroke, please specify	63.0	37.0
Do you know any warning signs of stroke, please specify	48.0	52.0
Stroke is an old man's disease	93.5	6.5
Stroke is a contagious disease	2.0	98.0
Stroke a hereditary disease	78.5	21.5
Aggregate score of knowledge	Frequency	Percent (%)
Good	168	84.0
Poor	32	16.0

Socio-Demographic Relationship of HealthCare Workers with Knowledge of Stroke Prevention

There was a significant association between good knowledge of stroke with gender

($p=0.015$), age above 30 years ($p=0.041$), having tertiary education ($p=0.014$), and among clinical Healthcare workers ($p=0.0001$) (Table 3).

Table3. Socio-Demographic Relationship of HealthCare Workers with Knowledge of Stroke Prevention

Variables	Good knowledge (%)	Poor knowledge (%)	Chi-square	P-value	95%CI
Gender			5.596	0.015	(1.152-5.478)
Male	67(77.0)	20(23.0)			
Female	101(89.4)	12(10.6)			

Age(years)			2.894	0.041	(0.155-1.166)
<=30	51(91.1)	5(8.9)			
>30	117(81.3)	27(18.7)			
Marital Status			0.745	0.252	(0.651-3.013)
Not married	60(81.1)	14(18.9)			
Married	108(85.7)	18(14.3)			
Educational Level			9.136	0.014	(1.668-37.005)
Poorly Educated	3(42.9)	4(57.1)			
Tertiary Educated	165(85.5)	28(14.5)			
Profession			27.1	0.0001	(0.029-0.256)
Clinical Healthcare workers	105(96.3)	4(3.7)			
Non-clinical Healthcare workers	63(69.2)	28(30.8)			
Religion			3.893	0.083	(0.050-1.109)
Christianity	164(85)	29(15)			
Non-Christians	4(57.1)	3(42.9)			

Socio-Demographic Predictor of Knowledge of Stroke Preventive Strategies among Healthcare Workers

The predictors of good knowledge of stroke were age above 30 years (95%CI= 0.082-0.865,

p=0.028) and clinical Healthcare workers (95%CI= 0.033-0.350, p=0.0001) (Table 4).

Table4. Socio-Demographic Predictor of Knowledge of Stroke Preventive Strategies among Healthcare Workers

Variables	B	Wald	P-value	odd ratio	95% CI for the odd ratio	
					Lower	Upper
Gender						
Male	-0.189	0.162	0.688	0.828	0.330	2.080
Female				1		
Age(years)						
<=30	-1.322	4.847	0.028	0.267	0.082	1.430
>30				1		
Marital Status						
Not married	.578	1.464	0.226	0.561	0.220	1.430
Married				1		
Educational Level						
Poorly Educated	1.273	2.093	0.148	3.570	0.637	20.027
Tertiary Educated				1		
Profession						
Clinical HCW	-2.226	13.739	<0.0001	0.108	0.033	0.350
Non-Clinical HCW				1		
Religion						
Christianity	-671	0.559	0.455	0.511	0.088	2.970
Non-Christians				1		

The Practice of Stroke Prevention among Respondents

Almost 61% of the Respondents had a poor aggregate practice of stroke prevention. The poor stroke prevention practices observed commonly among the respondents include; -

they will sprinkle water over the face of the person who has a stroke (89%), waiting for spontaneous recovery for individuals who have stroke (85.5%), not checking their blood pressure regularly or advise others to do so (70%), they do not exercise regularly or counsel

others to do so(61%) and will not check their cholesterol level or advise others to do so(56.5%) (Table5).

Table5. The Practice of Stroke Prevention among Respondents

Practice Questions	Yes (%)	No (%)
I will immediately sprinkle water over the face of the person who has stroke	11	89
I will call or take the stroke patient immediately to the hospital	81.5	8.5
I will wait for spontaneous recovery for individuals that have stroke	14.5	85.5
Do you control your cholesterol level or advise others to do so?	43.5	56.5
I check my blood pressure regularly and advise others to do so	30	70
Do you regularly exercise or counsel others to do so?	39	61
Do you try to lose weight or advise others regularly to do so?	46.5	53.5
I check my blood sugar level regularly and advise others to do so who are diabetes	46	54
Cigarette smoking is discouraged to prevent stroke	84.5	15.5
I do a dietary regimen to prevent stroke	69	31
I will not give home remedies immediately person has a stroke and will not advise others to do the same	64.5	35.5
Aggregate Practice of Stroke Prevention	Frequency	Percent (%)
Good	78	39
Poor	122	61

Socio-demographic Relationship of Healthcare Workers with the Practice of Stroke Prevention

There was a significant association between poor practice of stroke prevention with gender ($p=0.006$), and profession ($p=0.04$) (Table 6).

Table6. Socio-Demographic Relationship of Healthcare Workers with the Practice of Stroke Prevention

Variables	Good knowledge (%)	Poor knowledge (%)	Chi-square	P-value	95%CI
Gender			7.035	0.006	(0.257-1.266)
Male	43(49.4)	44(50.6)			
Female	35(31.0)	78(69.0)			
Age(years)			0.140	0.414	(0.472-1.664)
<=30	23(41.1)	33(58.9)			
>30	55(38.2)	89(61.8)			
Marital Status			0.067	0.458	(0.599-1.950)
Not married	28(37.8)	46(62.2)			
Married	50(39.7)	76(60.3)			
Educational Level			0.332	0.440	(0.307-8.584)
Poorly Educated	2(28.6)	5(71.4)			
Tertiary Educated	76(39.4)	117(60.6)			
Profession			3.570	0.04	(0.321-1.023)
Clinical Healthcare workers	49(45.0)	60(55.0)			
Non-clinical Healthcare workers	29(31.9)	62(68.1)			
Religion			0.332	0.440	(0.116-3.255)
Christianity	76(39.4)	117(60.6)			
Non-Christians	2(28.6)	5(71.4)			

Socio-demographic Predictor of Poor Practice of Stroke Preventive Strategies among Healthcare Workers

The predictors of the poor practice of stroke prevention were gender (95%CI=1.771-7.030,

p=0.0001) and profession (95%CI=0.167-0.693, p=0.003) (Table 7).

Table7. Socio-Demographic Predictor of Practice of Stroke Preventive Strategies among Healthcare Workers

Variables	B	Wald	P-value	odd ratio	95% CI for the odd ratio	
					Lower	Upper
Gender						
Male	1.261	12.855	0.0001	3.529	1.771	7.030
Female				1		
Age(years)						
<=30	-.266	0.459	0.498	0.767	0.356	1.653
>30				1		
Marital Status						
Not married	-.044	0.015	0.904	0.956	0.464	1.972
Married				1		
Educational Level						
Poorly Educated	0.050	0.003	0.957	1.051	0.168	6.587
Tertiary Educated				1		
Profession						
Clinical HCW	-1.077	8.837	0.003	0.341	0.167	0.693
Non-Clinical HCW				1		
Religion						
Christianity	-.233	0.064	0.801	0.792	0.129	4.860
Non-Christians				1		

Discussion

Primary prevention of stroke is better and cheaper than treatment of stroke and the global cost of strokes is an average of between €610-€220,822.45 based on the cost of the illness (Lucas-Noll, et al., 2023). Good awareness and knowledge of stroke, risk factors, and warning signs are vital for early practice of stroke prevention (Alhowaymel, et al., 2023). Therefore, in this study, we sought to investigate sociodemographic predictors of knowledge and practice of stroke preventive strategies among Healthcare workers in Nigeria. In the current study, most respondents were female Clinical Healthcare workers (figure 1), younger adults above 30 years of age, married, and had a tertiary education (table1). In the study done in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Alhowaymel, et al., 2023), they were mostly males, younger adults,

not married, who had a college degree or above. In another study conducted in Nigeria, subjects were predominantly females (65.7%), and had formal education (71.5%) (Arisege, et al., 2018) contrary, in a community study done in Ghana, most of the participants were males (54%) (Donkor, et al., 2014), not married (62%)and attended mostly secondary education(52%) (Donkor, et al., 2014). The majority of the respondents in our study had good aggregate knowledge of stroke (84%) and they knew that stroke is a disease of the brain (87.5%), largely preventable (93.5%) and if treated early (94.5%), will have a positive effect on individuals daily life activities (95.5%) (table2). This is similar to the study done in Sokoto (Arisege, et al., 2018) Nigeria. Many of the respondents were aware that the organ or parts of the body affected by stroke was the brain (89.1%). The majority of them also had good knowledge of the signs or

symptoms of stroke (87.0%). However, the community knowledge and awareness of stroke risk factors and warning signs in Ghana was sub-optimal, when they were asked which organ of the body was associated with stroke 24, 40% of the respondents correctly mentioned the brain. The gaps identified in the knowledge of stroke among the respondents in that study underscore the need for healthcare professionals to give sufficient attention to educating their patients on stroke, and the signs and symptoms of the disease at every clinic visit. Also, there is a need for community-based education programs to increase public awareness of stroke. This would enable them to seek care early enough, to prevent disease deterioration, and prevent serious complications.

In our study there was a significant association between good knowledge of stroke with gender (female sex) ($p=0.015$), age above 30 years ($p=0.041$), having tertiary education ($p=0.014$), and among clinical Healthcare workers ($p=0.0001$) (Table 3). The predictors of good knowledge of stroke were age above 30 years (95%CI= 0.082-0.865, $p=0.028$) and clinical Healthcare workers (95%CI= 0.033-0.350, $p=0.0001$) (Table 4). Therefore adult clinical Healthcare workers were found to be determinants of good aggregate knowledge for stroke prevention when compared with other sociodemographic variables in our study. Similarly in the study conducted in Sokoto Nigeria among hypertensive and diabetes patients (Arisege, et al., 2018). However, there was a significant association ($p < 0.05$) between good knowledge of stroke prevention and age below 50 years, female sex, having formal education, and being employed. However, the predictors of good knowledge of stroke prevention were having formal education and being employed. Respondents with formal education were approximately three times more likely to have good knowledge of stroke prevention as compared to those with no formal education only (aOR = 2.983, 95% CI = 1.351-6.588, $p = 0.007$) (Arisege, et al., 2018). They found well-educated adults correlated with good knowledge of stroke prevention. This is in tandem with the findings in a survey conducted

in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Nigeria (Okonkwo, et al., 2021). They found that Female participants, with a postgraduate level qualification and working as senior non-teaching staff, had a better awareness of stroke risk factors than their male colleagues (Okonkwo, et al., 2021).

In this study, there was a significant association between poor practice of stroke prevention with gender ($p=0.006$), and profession ($p=0.04$) (Table6) and they were found also to be the predictors of poor practice of stroke prevention [gender (95%CI=1.771-7.030, $p=0.0001$) and profession (95%CI=0.167-0.693, $p=0.003$) respectively (Table7)]. We found out that female Non-clinical healthcare workers in Federal Medical Centre Asaba, Nigeria, are more likely to have poor practice of stroke prevention when compared to male Clinical Healthcare workers counterparts. In the study done in Ethiopia (Tibebu, et al., 2021), about 24.9% (95% CI; 20.7, 29.3) of the participants had poor practice of stroke prevention, which is lower than the study conducted in Nigeria (Wahab, Kayode, & Musa, 2015) (90.8%, 49.4%) (Arisege, et al., 2018; Vincent-Onabajo, & Moses, 2016), Vienna (77%) (Tibebu, et al., 2021), and Kerala (78.3%) (Tibebu, et al., 2021) India. This inconsistency might be due to differences in the socioeconomic and socio-demographic attributes of the participants. But, it is higher than the study conducted in China (30%) (Wan, et al., 2014). The other probable reason might be due to population size which may not address the information regarding knowledge on stroke prevention modalities. They discovered that age was one of the predictors of knowledge on stroke prevention among hypertensive patients. Younger-aged hypertensive patients were 2.08 times more likely to have good stroke prevention knowledge than older-aged patients [AOR: 2.08 (1.07-4.049)]. The reason alluded to may be due to younger persons were occupied with using different technologies to get stroke-related information, whereas older individuals were not. The other predictor of knowledge on stroke prevention among hypertensive patients was the residence. Urban residents were 3.23 times more likely to have good knowledge of stroke

prevention than those who were in rural [AOR: 3.23 (1.665–6.267)]. The result is supported by the research done in Nigeria (Wahab, et al., 2015). The possible reasons might be due to the availability of accessed information in urban than rural areas. In Nigeria, a study showed that healthcare workers suffered limitations in providing adequate information on secondary stroke prevention to stroke survivors and their caregivers due to their heavy work schedule and the additional time that might be needed (Hurst, et al., 2015).

Limitation of the Study

Since the study was Hospital-based, there is a generalization of the findings of this study to the general population. Secondly, it was restricted to Healthcare workers, therefore results may not be the same with patients who were not healthcare workers. Moreover, the study was cross-sectional and we used a close-ended structured questionnaire. This might have restricted the participants' responses regarding their knowledge and practice of stroke prevention modalities. Other sociodemographic variables that were omitted were income and Residence.

Conclusion

The study revealed that Healthcare worker's knowledge about stroke prevention was good with poor practice. Being old age, clinical Healthcare workers were found to be likely predictors of good knowledge of stroke prevention while poor practice of stroke prevention was found to be associated more with female Non-clinical healthcare workers in our environment. These findings have immense importance for different stakeholders who have responsibilities for the reduction of the Burden of stroke. Healthcare professionals especially those that are directly involved in the care of stroke patients must therefore rise to the occasion. Female non-clinical Healthcare workers have to create more time for stroke education on preventive strategies. Similarly, the government and relevant policymakers must see the condition as a call to action by putting in

place necessary strategies that will facilitate and enhance stroke Prevention.

Reference

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